

TEACHING ORAL SPEECH IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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***Abstract.** The methodology of teaching a foreign language is one of the important tasks in teaching in general. Currently, active international interaction indicates that learning a foreign language using traditional methods requires revision. This article briefly discusses the features of teaching oral foreign language speech.*

***Keywords:** language, method, foreign, difficulties, oral speech, features of oral speech, communication, communicator*

Oral utterance differs from written speech primarily in the direct nature of communication, the presence of live contact between communicants, which, of course, leaves a strong imprint on the method and form of presentation of thoughts. The presence of a speech partner or simply listeners makes it possible for the speaker to catch the slightest reaction of his partners in a speech act, and this makes it possible to quickly respond to the further course of the presentation of thoughts in oral form.

Of course, educational oral speech with these characteristics may differ significantly from that which can be heard from the lips of native speakers entering into dialogue in some narrow area of communication. However, its advantage in methodological terms is that it, being understandable to everyone who speaks a given language, and, in addition, it is, as a rule, simpler in forms of expression, more standardized, which makes it easier to master its basics and use it for the purpose of communications [2].

Taking into account the peculiarities of teaching a foreign language in a higher educational institution requires special attention to the problem of the stylistic correlation between native speech and foreign language speech. There are many classifications of the stylistic affiliation of speech to one or another layer of language. In this regard, scientific, official business, journalistic, colloquial, everyday and artistic styles are more often distinguished (according to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov). It should be noted that foreign language teaching is also carried out in non-linguistic educational institutions. Depending on the profile of a non-linguistic

higher educational institution, on the stage of training and, of course, on the program, one or another style (or a combination of several styles) will dominate in the proposed educational materials, which should contribute to a more successful solution of specific educational tasks [1].

Linguistically, three forms of oral utterance are further distinguished: monologue, dialogue and polylogue. By polylogue we mean a combination, such as in a conversation, dialogue and monologue. But the possibilities from the point of view of language teaching methods did not pay enough attention to polylogue as a method of communication, so we can assume that in the methodological plan of developing foreign language lessons, it is possible to use the possibilities of polylogue to achieve results in learning [5].

Oral speech is also of important psychological interest. Under the influence of various information technologies in the psychology of oral speech, they increasingly began to distinguish between two communicative processes that combine with each other: listening with understanding (listening) and speaking itself, often called expressive speech by methodologists in order to distinguish between the concepts of oral speech in general and speaking (pronunciation) [3].

Sometimes in teaching aids devoted to teaching oral foreign language, such features as motivation, focus, emotionality and situationality are especially emphasized as its leading characteristics. Despite the highly specific capabilities of oral speech, written speech is also significant. It should be noted that written speech also has the noted characteristics, which, however, are expressed using means other than the means of oral communication. It should be emphasized that, for obvious reasons, the degree of emotionality and situationality of oral speech is incomparably higher than that which can be observed in a written text, even describing situations of oral communication (a play, a movie script or a television show). This is explained by the direct contact of the oral speech act, which is absent in the sphere of communication of written speech; there, as they say, an invisible contact is established only thanks to the very high skill of the author of the work [4].

Psychologically, the factor of preparedness and unpreparedness of a statement becomes of great importance. A prepared utterance is always based on volitional efforts, on purposeful voluntary memorization of linguistic material, on imitation, if sound samples are used for preparation. The situation is more complicated with the phenomenon of unpreparedness itself, which can be expressed at different levels of complexity and in various combinations of previously learned material. Thus, an unprepared utterance can be considered one that uses a new combination of known linguistic units (phrases, speech patterns, grammatical structures); he can be

considered unprepared even when the student correctly uses language material in a completely new situation; an utterance that is a reaction to a heard (not memorized) remark should be considered as unprepared, and, finally, everything that is offered as spontaneous, without any preparation in time, also undoubtedly bears the features of unpreparedness.

The motivation for learning a foreign language by students of higher educational institutions requires special attention in psychological terms. If in secondary school a student often does not see the immediate benefit in mastering a foreign language, which the teacher has to overcome at the cost of great effort, then the student wants to comprehensively master his special subject, and he understands that a good command of a foreign language will provide him with invaluable help as when reading specialized literature, and in direct communication with foreign colleagues in future work.

From a psychological point of view, the question of thinking in a foreign language seems very important. Thinking, as is known, can be verbal and also non-verbal. If we are talking about the possibility of achieving thinking in a foreign language, then this task can be solved even in a non-linguistic university, but within rather limited limits. Of course, such thinking in the forms of a foreign language will never become similar to thinking in the native language, since it will always contain, in a more or less pronounced form, an instant translation into the native language. When learning, it should always be taken into account. Only in conditions of continuous foreign language practice, supported by samples of correct speech coming from the environment, can a student achieve thinking in a foreign language. Conditions close to these exist only in educational institutions, the program of which provides for several thousand hours allocated to the course of study.

Having examined in the most general and extremely laconic form the most important linguistic and psychological issues of teaching oral foreign language speech, we should move on to a brief description of the methodological basis for teaching this type of speech activity. First of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the significant difficulties of teaching oral foreign language speech, caused, firstly, by the very nature of this type of speech activity and, secondly, by the conditions in which the educational process in a foreign language is carried out at a university with non-linguistic specialties.

Unlike a graphic code, an oral speech code is implemented in such a way that this process is highly dynamic. What is said or heard, unless it is recorded by a special technical device, is always relatively short-term and irreversible. Oral speech cannot be returned to again and again; it is very difficult to control without creating

unnecessary interference for the speaker or listener. This is a great difficulty from a methodological point of view.

The second methodological difficulty is due to the fact that oral speech is a process, as a rule, two-way: one communicator speaks, the other listens. Consequently, when teaching oral speech, it is necessary to teach students two types of speech activity - listening and speaking, each of which requires its own special exercises.

The next difficulty in teaching oral speech lies in its extremely high degree of situationality and emotionality. Without the presence of a situation adequate to linguistic means, oral speech does not become a full-fledged means of communication; it is transferred to the sphere of only acoustic signals, built on the basis of the oral speech code and not having a communicative task.

And in conclusion, we note that to the difficulties listed above are added the difficulties that arise due to the lack of adapted textbooks and teaching aids that would take into account the specifics of oral foreign language speech, as well as manuals that would be specifically aimed at this object of study. In connection with the existing difficulties, important problems arise: the choice of an object for mastering oral speech, the definition of an educational unit, the selection of educational material, the organization of educational material and, finally, the choice of means of teaching oral foreign language.

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